

DIGITAL RESOURCES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

Devoted to the topic of current interest in modern teaching, namely using MALL and technical means in traditional classroom learning and self-education, this article is aimed at studying the kinds and characteristics of various digital resources, including MALL (Mobile Assisted Language Learning) and generalizing the available new material on this subject. The object of the study is the application of the available technical base in education and teaching. The subject of research is using MALL in a present-day foreign language educational setting. The advantages and disadvantages of technical means in teaching have been investigated in the article. The author has enumerated the types of mobile means, programs and devices in foreign language learning. Moreover, the variants of their practical usage have been provided.

In accordance with the aim and tasks of the paper, the systemic approach to teaching foreign languages, as well as theoretical principles of audio-visual method, were selected as the methodology of the study.

Modern challenges that teachers face when working with MALL technology have been analyzed, thus proving the growing need for increasing teachers' and students' motivation to exploit Mobile Assisted Language Learning. Employing new means suggests a need for a thorough study of recent technological advances as to their applicability in teaching foreign languages, which demonstrates the scientific novelty of the paper.

Regarding the pressing issue of increasing learner autonomy, it has been proved that MALL technology provides students with new ways to experience active learning and to explore other forms of academic cooperation, owing to the current demand for more individual activity of students in view of new opportunities made available by the digital progress.

To draw the conclusions, it should be noted that the experience of using some of the most up-to-date mobile devices to practice the target vocabulary or key grammar constructions stipulated in foreign language syllabi shows their potential in an ESL classroom.

Key words: digital resources, MALL, mobile technology, podcasts, foreign language teaching.

Establishing the problem. *The topical value of the paper lies in the current lack of a profound survey of the recent mobile devices to practice the target language units stipulated in a foreign language syllabus. Some teachers have already introduced new tools into today's ESL classrooms while others need more information and guidance regarding the educational value of such gadgets.*

Having browsed recent surveys and articles, we can state that a lot of foreign scientists have pointed out a need for shifting towards new ways of practicing foreign language material (D. Czarska-Andrzejewska, A. T. Damascelli, R. Kendall, G. Mansfield) in order to build strong lexical and grammatical skills. The researchers call for a variety of tools in order to ensure diversity of ways of employing target vocabulary and grammar with the aim to build a learner's identity able to meet modern labor market requirements.

Thus, the aim of this article is to study some peculiarities of employing up-to-date mobile devices in a foreign-language classroom.

The object of the study is the application of the available technical base in education and teaching.

The subject of research is using MALL in a present-day foreign language educational setting.

The methodology of the study included the systemic approach to teaching foreign languages, as well as theoretical principles of the audio-visual method to practicing target vocabulary and grammar.

The scientific novelty of the study lies in an attempt to study the peculiarities of work with the most up-to-date mobile devices in order to diversify academic process and boost students' motivation.

The results of the study. Being widely used in education digital resources have proved to demonstrate the need of modern educators to find new tools and ways to diversify academic process and at the same time teachers' openness to respond to recent developments in teaching practice. With students already immersed in their mobile devices, it is only reasonable to exploit this situation to the benefit of education.

The idea to use portable digital devices in education is not a new one, but nowadays educators can have a full overview of the possibilities associated with digital academic resources. When talking about digital devices we mean all computer based and hand-held resources available for users to download or exploit online such as blogs, podcasts, video storing sites, listening libraries, social networking.

Introducing digital resources into a foreign language classroom, we create a whole new dimension for developing students' digital and media literacy, computer proficiency.

The implementation of digital resources is closely connected with the notion of learner mobility and expansion of classroom limits. It is mobile learning that helps modern foreign language classes go beyond traditional student-teacher interaction. It is usually defined as «learning mediated via handheld devices and potentially available anytime, anywhere» [5, 273]. Mobility in education gives learners unrestricted access to learning materials and an unprecedented learning experience. Most importantly, mobile devices change the usual pattern of learner motivation and engagement.

It's worth mentioning that technological assistance in teaching can be of various kinds and according to Gillian Mansfield can be classified into high-tech, low-tech and no-tech assistance [8]:

- high-tech – suitable for a classroom where the teacher has an internet-enabled computer connected to a data projector, and students have access to enough internet-enabled computers or mobile devices to allow them to work in small groups, pairs or even individually;

- low-tech – suitable for a classroom where the teacher has an internet-enabled computer connected to a data projector, but students do not have access to internet-enabled computers or mobiles;

- no-tech suitable for a classroom where there is no internet-enabled computer available, although some of these activities require the teacher to access an internet-enabled computer outside the classroom and print materials to bring to the class [8, 43].

It's been argued that using podcasts in education «is innovative, engaging and rapidly increasing and it offers the potential to transform the learning experience significantly by facilitating the organization and delivery of information in ways more tailored than hitherto to individual learners' needs and learning styles» [6, 41–42].

Having studied a lot of research, we have distinguished the types of **Mobile Assisted Language Learning** as for form of work:

1. Individual (listening to podcasts and songs, reading news and other content, doing grammar exercises online, watching video clips, et cetera).

2. Collaborative:

- 2.1 learner-to-teacher (coaching for example);

- 2.2 learner-to-learner (chatting, talking to other learners via Skype, WhatsApp, Viber) [11].

The variety of types of MALL is constantly increasing and it is impossible to enumerate all the kinds existing, but among the most famous can be noted the following ones:

- SMS-based learning – quizzes, learning vocabulary – SMS learning drills vocabulary, writing, reading;

- video messaging – MMS;

- podcasting;

- GAME-based learning;

- Audio / video recording – drills speaking, listening;

- learning via the Internet – drills speaking, reading, listening, writing;

- using IP telephony – Skype – drills speaking, understanding, listening to native speakers;

- micro blogging – drills use of English, speaking;

- Tablet Computing.

SMS-based learning is primarily used to boost the vocabulary. For example, a teacher can send a word at equal intervals to the learner. It may also be a «make-up a story» activity when several learners create their own story by writing each a sentence or two and sending them to the next student.

Podcasting is a kind of MALL used for improving listening skills. As a rule, podcasts have a specific thematic range, so the listener may choose a podcast to correspond his own preferences and needs. By listening to podcasts, a learner may not only train his or her understanding, but also improve pronunciation, intonation and boost the vocabulary.

Game-based learning. Most people use the Internet and wireless communications for relaxation and entertainment. As mobile devices are an integral part of modern life, academic learning may become boring and coercive. In this case, a game may be a perfect means that combines entertainment and a very effective learning. Games are considered to be mainly used beyond the classroom but in modern times, there are a large variety of platforms with games for playing during classes. A famous example is Kahoot, a website with multiple-choice quizzes, used for educational purposes at schools. All the students with smart phones and the Internet access may take part and compete with each other.

Audio / video recording can be used by teachers to identify students' mistakes while speaking. That is a teacher records the students' communication and later checks if the students mind their grammar while speaking. Another way of using audio / video recording may be performing a small play or doing some interview activity that can be captured and stored.

Learning via the Internet can be various. Students may check e-mails, read online news, watch videos, and do whatever they fancy. Students may also download music, e-books, apps, online and offline dictionaries. Learners can also share these items via Bluetooth.

Using IP telephony. As it has already been stated, programs created to communicate may become a means of exchanging cultural values, improving speaking, listening and understanding skills as a student may find and socialize with unlimited number of native and non-native speaker.

Micro blogging is one of the most efficient ways of learners' using of language because it empowers them to perform and to practice the obtained knowledge. Taking into account that apart from traditional blogging students can be engaged in video- and audioblogging it may become an interesting and useful experience of informal interaction and intercultural communication [3].

Tablet Computing is a subtype of MALL that is presented as an alternative to cell phones and overcomes the problems like small screen and data storage capacity.

Applying wireless technologies has a list of indisputable advantages, among which there are the following features [8]:

- Portability.
- Social interactivity (exchanging of the data).
- Context sensitivity (gathering exclusive data to the place and time).
- Connectivity of devices between each other.
- Individuality.

Among other advantages we may distinguish:

- Learning outside the classroom.
- Making learning pleasurable and in line with reality.

Among the disadvantages of mobile devices researchers point out the following:

- small screen / keypad;
- difficulty while reading on a screen;
- data storage;
- multimedia and graphics limitations;
- the cost of Internet access on the mobile phone;
- some mobile phones are not designed for educational purposes, thus teachers should be aware of what kind of tools learners have and set or adapt resources compatible to such tools;
- dependence on networks that may not provide very high transmission capacity and may be subject to disturbances of many kinds [3, 45-46].

To **conclude** all the stated above, there is a strong need to emphasize that learning using mobile technologies is becoming more and more accepted by the new generation of students as handheld devices are an inherent part of modern life. Now this subject is being intensively developed and new types of MALL emerge, but we can distinguish the most popular ones between them, like SMS-based learning, podcasting, game-based learning, audio / video recording, learning via the Internet, using IP telephony, micro blogging and tablet computing.

Further research will focus on the peculiarities of the implementation of various kinds of MALL in a foreign language setting.

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ЦИФРОВІ РЕСУРСИ У НАВЧАННІ АНГЛІЙСЬКОЇ МОВИ

Стаття присвячена актуальній для сучасної освіти темі – використання мобільних пристроїв і технічних засобів під час аудиторних занять та самостійного навчання.

Мета статті – дослідити види та характеристики різноманітних цифрових пристроїв, включаючи мобільні засоби навчання, а також узагальнити наявний новий матеріал з цієї теми. Об'єктом дослідження є застосування технічної бази в освіті та навчанні. Предметом дослідження було обрано використання мобільних пристроїв у професійній діяльності викладачів.

Відповідно до мети і завдань роботи, в якості **методологічної бази** дослідження було обрано системний підхід до навчання іноземних мов, а також теоретичні засади аудіо-візуального методу.

Застосування нових технічних засобів вимагає їх глибокого дослідження в аспекті придатності до використання в освітньому середовищі, що й обумовлює **наукову новизну** роботи.

У статті досліджено переваги та недоліки технічних засобів у процесі навчання. Наведено різновиди мобільних засобів, програм та пристроїв, які використовуються під час вивчення іноземної мови, а також авторка надала варіанти їхнього практичного використання.

Сучасні виклики, з якими стикаються викладачі під час застосування мобільних технологій, вказують на зростаючу потребу в підвищенні мотивації як викладачів, так і студентів до більш ефективного використання цифрових ресурсів на заняттях. Використання нових засобів навчання потребує детального вивчення останніх технічних новинок стосовно їхнього дидактичного потенціалу, що обумовлює **наукову новизну** проведеного дослідження.

Зважаючи на сучасну тенденцію до навчальної автономії студента, слід зауважити, що мобільні засоби навчання надають студентам нові способи втілення принципу активного навчання та спонукають до інших форм академічної співпраці, завдяки надбанням технічного прогресу. Порівнюється застосування мобільних засобів навчання в межах організації навчального процесу в іншомовній освіті.

Підсумовуючи результати дослідження, варто зазначити, що, незважаючи на певні технічні недоліки, досвід використання деяких найсучасніших мобільних засобів навчання з метою відпрацювання активного словника та граматичних конструкцій, демонструє їх значний дидактичний потенціал.

Ключові слова: викладання іноземних мов, мобільні засоби навчання, мобільні технології, подкасти, цифрові ресурси.

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